

ISic0374

I.Sicily inscription 0374

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR141188

1. D (is) M (anibus) s (acrum)
2. [---]atiae Dori
3. [di] v (ixit) a (nnis) XX Nice
4. [phor] pater filiae
5. [pii]ssimae.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491585

EDR 141188

EDCS 21900414

Bibliography

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliae obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ,

cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.60
Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae
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CILv10pII1883](http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883))

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edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4384367>